

different DNA extraction and purification procedures in parallel: 1) treatment of the seed concentrate by a heat shock or 2) use of the DNeasy Plant Mini Kit columns (Qiagen). Thirteen ELISA positive samples were found: from those seed samples, 5000 seeds for each extraction method were taken and extracted according to the two procedures mentioned above. Results highlighted that ELISA performed quite well, but the most sensitive and reliable pathogen detection was done by seed extraction with the DNeasy Plant Mini Kit, followed by simplex-PCR. Direct isolation and simplex-PCR following heat shock gave several false negative results. Genotyping of a *X. euvesicatoria* isolate collection was attempted through rep-PCR, using the BOX, REP and ERIC primers to specifically amplify repetitive elements dispersed throughout the bacterial genome. Results highlighted that *X. euvesicatoria* is quite a uniform population, taxonomically not so distant from *X. perforans*, but clearly distinguished from the other two xanthomonads. Analysis of BOX-PCR profiles supports the fact that a possible *X. euvesicatoria* subgroup is present in the main population, which might be related to a different geographical origin of seeds.

16. CHARACTERIZATION OF SELECTED CITRUS-ASSOCIATED *ALTERNARIA* ISOLATES. F. Garganese¹, S.M. Sanzani¹, L. Schena², A. Ippolito¹. ¹Department of Soil, Plant and Food Sciences (DiSSPA), University of Bari "Aldo Moro", Via G. Amendola 165/A, I-70126 Bari, Italy. ²Department of Agriculture, Mediterranean University of Reggio Calabria, Via Salita Melissari, Località Feo di Vito, I-89124 Reggio Calabria, Italy. E-mail: simonamarianna.sanzani@uniba.it

Alternaria brown spot is one of the most important diseases of tangerines and their hybrids worldwide. Recently, a disease outbreak in Southern Italy refocused the attention on the disease. Twenty representative cultures of *Alternaria* were selected from a collection of more than 100 isolates from leaves and fruits of cvs. Fortune, Nova, Valencia, and Tangerine. Then, they were characterized along with specimen strains of *A. tenuissima*, *A. alternata*, *A. arborescens*, *A. citri*, *A. toxicogenica*, and *A. limoniasperae* ("small-spored" *Alternaria* species) to determine the etiology of the disease and evaluate the virulence of different isolates/species. Morphological characteristics and sporulation patterns separated most *Alternaria* isolates into three main groups corresponding to *A. alternata*, *A. arborescens*, and *A. tenuissima*, of which the first was the most abundant one. Phylogenetic analyses based on endopolygalacturonase (endoPG) and β -tubulin genes, two anonymous genomics regions (OPA 1-3 and OPA 2-1), and the Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) region produced a clustering of isolates largely confirming morphological results. The OPA 1-3 region was more suitable than other tested regions for separating closely related "small-spored" *Alternaria* species and revealed the existence of intra-species molecular variability. Investigated isolates showed different levels of virulence on leaves and fruits but it was not possible to identify a direct correlation between virulence and genetic/morphological groupings of isolates.

17. ADOPTION OF HIGH THROUGHPUT SEQUENCING FOR ASSESSING THE OUTRIGHT SANITARY STATUS OF CERTIFIED GRAPEVINE CLONES AND ROOTSTOCKS. A. Giampetruzzi¹, M. Morelli¹, M. Chiumentini¹, V.N. Savino², G.P. Martelli², P. La Notte^{1,3}, F. Palmisano³, P. Saldarelli¹. ¹National Research Council of Italy, Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection (IPSP), Via G. Amendola 122/D, I-70126 Bari, Italy. ²Department of Soil, Plant and Food Sciences (DiSSPA), University of Bari "Aldo Moro", Via G. Amendola 165/A, I-70126 Bari, Italy. ³Centre for Research, Experimentation and Education in Agriculture (CRSFA)

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For a thorough characterization of their virome, 20 selected clones of grapevine cultivars and rootstocks, maintained in the premultiplication plots of the CRSFA (Centre for Research, Experimentation and Education in Agriculture "Basile Caramia", Locorotondo, Italy), were subjected to High Throughput Sequencing (HTS). Prior to the present study, which was developed in the frame of the Apulian Regional project Re.Ge.Vi.P. ("Recovery of Apulian grape germplasm"), certified grapevine accessions were known to be free from viruses and diseases regulated in the Italian certification system, as assessed by time-consuming and narrow-range specific assays, i.e. Wood Indexing (WI) and serological or RT-PCR molecular tests. The HTS of small RNA (sRNA) libraries, performed on an Illumina HiScan SQ™ apparatus, and data processing through a custom-developed bioinformatic pipeline, confirmed the absence of the following regulated viruses: *Grapevine virus A* (GVA), *Grapevine virus B* (GVB), *Grapevine leafroll-associated virus 1, 2 and 3* (GLRaV-1, -2, -3), *Grapevine fanleaf virus* (GFLV), *Grapevine fleck virus* (GFkV) and *Arabis mosaic virus* (ArMV), allowing an in-depth analysis also of viral and viroidal infections. This unbiased approach disclosed the presence of agents that are not targeted in routinely performed assays, like *Grapevine rupestris stem pitting-associated virus* (GRSPaV), *Grapevine rupestris vein feathering virus* (GRVfV), *Hot stunt viroid* (HSVd) and *Grapevine yellow speckle viroid 1* (GYSVd-1), in addition to hitherto unknown viruses, such as a new badnavirus-like species, showing similarities to *Grapevine roditis leaf discoloration-associated virus* (GRLDaV). Our findings, although requiring further standardization efforts, highlight the potential benefits of using the HTS approach in grapevine certification schemes, in substitution for, or in synergy with WI and conventional laboratory tests.

18. NEW *COLLETOTRICHUM* spp. ON ORNAMENTAL PLANTS IN NORTHERN ITALY. G. Gilardi^{1,2}, G. Ortu¹, S. Franco Ortega¹, M.L. Gullino^{1,2}, A. Garibaldi¹. ¹Centre of Competence for the Innovation in the Agro-Environmental Field – AGROINNOVA, University of Torino, Largo Paolo Braccini 2, I-10095 Grugliasco (TO), Italy. ²Department of Agricultural, Forestry and Food Sciences (DISAFA), University of Torino, Largo Paolo Braccini 2, I-10095 Grugliasco (TO), Italy. E-mail: giovanna.gilardi@unito.it

Anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum* spp. is one of the most common disease on many ornamentals. During the summer-fall 2014, previously unreported leaf spots were observed on plants of *Salvia leucantha* and *S. greggii* grown in a garden located near Biella (Northern Italy) at an altitude of 800 m. All plants were affected, though at different level. The first symptoms consisted in small necrotic spots interesting a large percentage of the leaf, which eventually wilted. Generally, the disease started from basal leaves on plants grown in shadow and at higher RH. On the basis of several isolations carried out on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) amended with 25 mg L⁻¹ of streptomycin sulphate from infected tissues, *Colletotrichum* sp. was consistently recovered from infected tissues of *S. leucantha*, and *S. greggii*. The pathogenicity of the different strains of *Colletotrichum* were confirmed under controlled conditions and re-isolation of fungal isolates showing the same morphological characteristics as *Colletotrichum*, fulfilling Koch's postulate. Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) analysis permitted to confirm such identification. This is to our knowledge the first report of anthracnose caused by different strains of *Colletotrichum* on *S. leucantha* and *S. greggii* in Italy, as well as in the world.